

How Leadership Promotes Employee Job Satisfaction: A Literature Review

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Abstract:- Employee job satisfaction greatly determines the level of employee performance in an organization. Employees who have a high level of job satisfaction will have loyal, disciplined, optimistic, professional, honest, responsible and other positive attitudes. Employee job satisfaction will be present if the leader plays his leadership well. This review literature aims to analyze how big the relationship between leadership and employee job satisfaction. The research method in this literature uses a systematic literature review. Research data was obtained through internet searches regarding employee job satisfaction journals published in 2014-2022. From the results of the research above, it can be seen that as many as 17 studies showed a positive and significant influence between leadership variables and employee job satisfaction. This means that if a person's leadership style is judged to be pro-employee, the leader will be loved by his employees, of course an employee will achieve satisfaction at work if led by a leader they love.

Keywords:- Leadership, Job Satisfaction, Literature Review.

I. INTRODUCTION

Employee satisfaction is one of the factors that determine a person's performance at work. High job satisfaction makes employees work happily, happily and enjoy their work. Of course this will make employees work as well as possible to achieve company goals. Job satisfaction of an employee can be seen from various things, including satisfaction with salary, satisfaction with awards, satisfaction with work facilities, satisfaction with leadership/supervision, satisfaction with fellow co-workers which means whether there is a good relationship between fellow employees, then satisfaction with opportunities and promotional fairness.

Every organization has one goal, namely to develop, progress and survive in the long term. To achieve this goal, each organization has a different strategy from one organization to another, one of which is the strategy for its human resources. Human resources are very important to carry out one function of the organization.

The functioning of an organization certainly does not escape the expertise of a leader in leading his employees. According to (Aditya et al., 2021) Character leadership has four main characteristics: being honest, looking far ahead, being able to inspire, and being competent. The combination

of these four characteristics forms credibility. Credible leaders can be trusted. The way to carry out character leadership is to set a real example for followers so that they are influenced to carry it out.

Leadership is one of the factors that can provide an increase in employee performance, and the achievement of the organization's vision and mission. Therefore, leaders must really be able to protect and motivate employees to work and improve employee performance. Leadership must be able to increase the level of employee job satisfaction (Dasaad, 2015). Employees who have high levels of job satisfaction will tend to be more committed and contribute and have high dedication to the company and ultimately have the will to work harder and be more productive. (Pitasari & Perdhana, 2018). Research conducted by (Aristana et al., 2021) said that the role of leaders in maintaining job satisfaction has been much proven in previous findings (Boamah et al., 2018; Liu et al., 2020; Cheung and Wong, 2011; Mufti et al., 2020).

The importance of the study of leadership and employee job satisfaction has been revealed in many previous studies. Apart from leadership, there are many variables that affect job satisfaction, such as: Work Environment, Work Motivation, Organizational Climate, Work Stress, Organizational Commitment, Salary, Communication, Organizational Culture (Astuti & Iverizkinawati, 2018); (Rivaldo & Ratnasari, 2020); (Heroes & Onsardi, 2020); (Gunawan & Sriathi, 2019); (Yuliana et al., 2020); (Hopefully, 2020); (Tambunan, 2019).

This literature review aims to present a review of the literature on leadership and employee job satisfaction. The results of this review are expected to provide information and references to increase employee job satisfaction in Indonesia.

II. METHOD

This research is a study using a literature study approach. Data was collected related to leadership and job satisfaction from 2014-2022. The number of journals analyzed were 20 journals. The data is used to identify and analyze leadership and employee job satisfaction.

III. FINDINGS

Based on the results of the analysis of the selected articles, it can be seen that there are many variables used to measure the relationship between employee job satisfaction.

The data in the selected articles, namely as many as 17 articles, are used to identify the extent of the relationship between leadership and other variables, as shown in the following table.

Table 1. Finding

Variable	Author	Results
Leadership, Job Satisfaction, Communication	Bedoya, (2021)	The research findings show that job satisfaction is influenced by leadership
Leadership, organizational culture, job satisfaction	Dimitrious Belias, (2014)	Leadership influences job satisfaction
Situational Leadership, Job Satisfaction, OCB, and Performance	Pasaribu et al., (2022)	Leadership can increase employee job satisfaction at work
Work Motivation, Organizational Climate And Leadership	Heroes & Onsardi, (2020)	The research findings show job satisfaction can be influenced by leadership
Organizational Culture, Work Motivation, Leadership	Tambunan, (2019)	Job satisfaction can be increased with good leadership.
Leadership and Job Satisfaction: Communication Mediation	Hope, (2020)	Leadership positively and significantly effect on job satisfaction
Leadership and Job Satisfaction, Communication	Aristana et al., (2021)	Leadership has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction.
Salary, Leadership Style	Yuliana et al., (2020)	Leadership has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction
Work Stress, Organizational Commitment, Leadership Style	Gunawan & Sriathi, (2019)	Good leadership style can increase employee job satisfaction at work
Leadership And Motivation	Rivaldo & Ratnasari, (2020)	Leadership directly has a positive but not significant effect on job satisfaction.
Organizational Culture, Work Motivation, Leadership Style	Hidayat et al., (2018)	Leadership style has a significant effect on job satisfaction. It can be concluded that a good leadership style will have an impact on job satisfaction at the Rokan Hilir Regency gas station.
Leadership Style	Sinurat, (2017)	Job satisfaction increases with good leadership
Leadership And Job Satisfaction	Dasaad, (2015)	The results of the study show that there is an influence between leadership on employee job satisfaction
Compensation, Work Climate, Leadership	Tampubolon, (2021)	Employee perceptions of leadership affect employee job satisfaction in carrying out their duties
The Influence of Organizational Culture, Leadership Style	Ali et al., (2018)	Leadership style has no positive and significant effect on job satisfaction, but has a positive and significant effect on employee performance.
Leadership, Work Environment	Astuti & Iverizkinawati, (2018)	The results of this study indicate that there is a positive influence of leadership variables on employee job satisfaction
Motivation, Leadership	Adam et al., (2021)	Leadership effect employee job satisfaction positively.

IV. DISCUSSION

From the results of the research above, it can be seen that as many as 17 studies showed a positive and significant influence between leadership variables and employee job satisfaction. This means that if a person's leadership style is judged to be pro-employee, the leader will be loved by his employees, of course an employee will achieve satisfaction at work if led by a leader they love. This is in line with (Charis et al., 2020) who said that, the organization will run well if its leadership is led by a leader who is loved by his subordinates.

Good leadership is fostering enthusiasm and motivation of employees to achieve organizational goals, not making

employees feel threatened at work. Every leader is required to be a role model, uphold ethical values so that they can be a good example for employees. A leader must also be able to provide good and clear directions to realize the ideals of the organization. Employees will feel happy, and not feel threatened if the leader plays a good leadership role at work, and the implication is that job satisfaction and employee performance increase.

Other variables that are also considered to affect employee job satisfaction such as: (1) motivation studied by Heroes & Onsardi, (2020); (Tambunan, 2019); (Rivaldo & Ratnasari, 2020); (Hidayat et al., 2018) describes a positive and significant relationship to employee job satisfaction. But

research conducted by (Adam et al., 2021) illustrates the results that employee motivation has no significant effect on employee job satisfaction. However, motivation and leadership mediated by employee job satisfaction have a strong influence on employee performance (2) Organizational Climate researched by (Heroes & Onsardi, 2020) illustrates the existence of a significant influence on employee job satisfaction. (3) Organizational Culture researched by (Tambunan, 2019); (Ali et al., 2018) illustrates the existence of a positive and significant relationship to employee job satisfaction. But research conducted by (Hidayat et al., 2018) that Organizational Culture variable has no effect on Job Satisfaction. It can be concluded that even though the organizational culture is good, it does not necessarily increase job satisfaction at gas stations in Rokan Hilir Regency. (4) Salary and Compensation researched by (Yuliana et al., 2020); (Tampubolon, 2021) illustrates the results, there is a positive relationship with employee job satisfaction. (5) Work stress studied by (Gunawan & Sriathi, 2019) gives a negative result on employee job satisfaction, which means that the higher the work stress felt by employees, the lower the job satisfaction of employees to remain in organizations in the company. (6) Organizational commitment examined by (Gunawan & Sriathi, 2019) gives the result of a positive influence on employee job satisfaction, which means that the better the organizational commitment applied to the company, the higher the job satisfaction of employees to remain committed to the company.

Thus, based on the literature review previously stated, it shows that leaders have a very crucial role in increasing employee job satisfaction. If the leader plays his leadership well, the employees will feel satisfied at work. Conversely, if the leader does not show a good leader, the employee will experience a decrease in job satisfaction.

V. CONCLUSION

The results of the literature review show that employee job satisfaction can increase through good leadership. Employee job satisfaction including job satisfaction with salary, satisfaction with facilities, satisfaction with co-worker relationships, satisfaction with fair promotion must really become the concern of the leader in organization. The finding show that leadership is a very important factor in increasing employee job satisfaction. If leadership carries out its duties well as a leader, employees will feel happy, comfortable and job satisfaction will increase. Recommendation for future research for future researchers to conduct further research on leadership and job satisfaction empirically, not only review literature.

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